

CRYPTO(Etherium)-Price Prediction Using RNN

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Abstract— More consumers and businesses are flocking to digital transactions as the Internet becomes more accessible and convenient. Digital payment systems are more efficient, faster, and less expensive. As a result, it's no surprise that new sorts of digital payment systems are rapidly emerging. No other approach even comes close to the size of cryptocurrencies when compared to it. Cryptocurrencies such as Bitcoin and Ethereum are among the most widely used forms of electronic money. Cryptocurrencies can be promoted in India as a viable digital currency choice, but both advantages and disadvantages must be understood. This research effort will study the cryptocurrency and its daily exchange rate through a literature review.

Keywords—Bitcoin,Cryptocurrency, Proof of work (POW), Virtual currency,Etherium

I. INTRODUCTION

Money is one of the most powerful motivators for people in today's world. Money in the form of identifiable denominations has been around for almost 3000 years. Humans have been trading through the exchange of commodities since the dawn of time. A system like this is referred to as barter. The types of money have evolved greatly over time, from precious metals to today's paper notes, but the core notion of cash has remained the same.

Money serves as a medium for trading goods without having to exchange them directly. This allows the client and seller to determine an appropriate price for each item. It doesn't matter what shape the money takes as long as it accomplishes the goal. In the end, the value of money is decided by the people who use it. With the dawn of the twenty-first century, the exponential rise of digital space, particularly the internet, has been astounding. It's no wonder that digital currencies are becoming more popular as the internet becomes more accessible.

Cryptocurrency is one of the most rapidly expanding types of digital currency. In layman's terms, cryptocurrency is a digitally encrypted currency that uses cryptography to manage and track transactions as well as verify their authenticity. In the year 2008, Satoshi Nakamoto (the first creator's pseudonym) attempted to create a peer-to-peer cash system that would not be stored in a central location. In the process, he unwittingly invented Bitcoin, the most popular cryptocurrency. Since then, Bitcoin has grown in popularity, with the current market price hovering at 1 Bitcoin equalling 30,000 us Dollar or more.

II. LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Current status, classification and open issues in Blockchain:

An investigation of the current state of blockchain technology and its applications is conducted, with the goal of highlighting how specific features of this disruptive technology can revolutionise "business-as-usual" procedures..[1]

Predicting Fluctuations in Cryptocurrency:

Predicting fluctuations using transactions to forecast volatility Based on user feedback and responses. analyses user comments in online cryptocurrency communities to forecast swings in bitcoin values and transaction volume. By concentrating on three cryptocurrencies with big market capitalizations and user bases, it is possible to predict such movements using a simple and effective strategy..[2]

Deep learning in predicting cryptocurrency volatility:

Stock market volatility is a significant factor that influences a wide range of business and financial decisions. Volatility spillovers between the bitcoin market and other financial markets have recently been observed. Despite this, bitcoin volatility projections fall short of market dynamics. To predict the volatility of three different cryptocurrencies, Bitcoin, Ripple, and Ethereum, empirical evidence is offered utilising data from three different cryptocurrencies.[3]

Cryptocurrency trading:

Spot trading volumes have a substantial favourable effect on price volatility, according to a study in financial-innovation-volume, but the relationship between cryptocurrency volatility and the derivative market is unclear.[4]

Cryptocurrency Market Analysis:

From the Open Innovation Perspective a proposal to the pool complexity approach to choose optimal technology using social activity in the internet, trading parameters, technical indicators and other

cryptocurrency data, to analyse the status of cryptos in market which helps in crypto trading.[5]

III. MOTIVATION

Since the launch of cryptocurrencies, they have been counted as one of the most fluctuating and volatile topics in the world, seeking to get to the bottom of what cryptocurrency is. Many of us due to its increase in popularity own different types of cryptos. But the fluctuations in rate affects the owners both positively and negatively. So a rate prediction system of crypto could help the crypto investors of buying and selling the cryptos by predicting the day by day value fluctuation.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The purpose of this paper is to find a Machine Learning model to predict the rate fluctuation (variations) of cryptocurrency named Ethereum using the given dataset with accuracy. The model should be able to classify predict the value of Ethereum. The dataset is divided into two training and testing data sets. The model should be trained with more data to get accuracy in learning. The result from this model can be used to buy or sell the crypto according to the predicted value. The RNN algorithm is the algorithm implemented in this paper, The structure is in figure 1:

Figure 1: Ethereum Value Prediction Methodology

The steps that required are:

1. Data Collection

2. Data Pre-processing
3. Model Building
4. Analyzing
5. Result

A. Data Collection: User have a dataset of exchange rates of Ethereum to USD, the attributes of this dataset is used to train the model. There 1528 rows and 4 columns in dataset. The columns are headings and label. The heading denotes the dates and opening and closing values of Ethereum respectively. These dataset are used to predict the value of Ethereum.

B. Machine Learning: This is used to predict the exchange rate of Ethereum to USD. The machine learning algorithms are used to predict the value, from the given dataset. There are different classifiers present to detect the fake news. The classifier accuracy relies on how it is trained. A classifier should need high accuracy. The algorithm used in this model is RNN:

1.RNN- The recurrent neural network is a type of sequential data algorithm. Because of its closed memory, it is the principal algorithm that retains its input, making it ideal for machine learning tasks involving sequential data. It is one of the deep learning algorithms that is used. RNNs can recall significant details about the input they receive thanks to their internal memory, allowing them to be quite precise when predicting what will happen next. This is why they are frequently used to process sequential data such as statistics, voice, text, financial data, audio, video, weather, and so on. In comparison to other algorithms, recurrent neural networks may acquire a far deeper grasp of a sequence and its context.

V. BUILD MODEL

The model building is the main step. While building the model user use the algorithms. The steps involved are:

1. Import the packages that are necessary.

```
from tensorflow.keras.models import Sequential
from tensorflow.keras.layers import Activation, Dense, Dropout
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
from sklearn.metrics import mean_absolute_error
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor
```

```
[ ] import sklearn
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
```

```
[ ] from tensorflow.python.keras.layers import SimpleRNNCell
from tensorflow.python.keras.layers import RNN
```

*importing necessary packages

2. Add the data into a Data-Frame, then get the shape of data.

```
data = pd.read_csv("ETH-USD_data.csv")
data = data.iloc[:,0:6]
y = data.loc[:,['Close']]
data = data.drop(['Close'],axis='columns')
print(data.head(5))
```

*reading dataset

3. Then split the dataset into training and testing datasets.

```
X_train = data[256:]
X_test = data[:256]

y_train = y[256:]
y_test = y[:256]
```

*splitting data

4. Then, fit and transform train and test set.

```
[ ] model = build_lstm_model(
    X_train, output_size=1, neurons=lstm_neurons, dropout=dropout, loss=loss,
    optimizer=optimizer)
modelfit = model.fit(
    X_train, y_train, validation_data=(X_test, y_test), epochs=epochs, batch_size=batch_size, verbose=1, shuffle=True)
```

*transforming dataset

5. Perform RNN .

```
from tensorflow.python.keras.layers import SimpleRNNCell
from tensorflow.python.keras.layers import RNN
def build_lstm_model(input_data, output_size, neurons, activ_func='tanh',
    dropout=0.21, loss='mse', optimizer='adam'):
    model = Sequential()
    #model.add(LSTM(neurons,activation="tanh",return_sequences=True))
    model.add(RNN(cell=[SimpleRNNCell(128),
        SimpleRNNCell(256),
        SimpleRNNCell(128)]))
    model.add(Dropout(dropout))
    model.add(Dense(units=output_size))
    model.add(Activation(activ_func))
```

*performing RNN algorithm

6. Then identify on test set and calculate the accuracy of the model.

```
[ ] accuracy = (dt/eth)
print( "accuracy: {:.2f}%".format(accuracy*100))
```

*calculating accuracy

The accuracy is 98.46%.

VI. RESULT

The result shows predicted exchange value of Ethereum on 24-february-2022, by considering the provided training and test dataset. also by comparing the true exchange value in this model we get an accuracy of 98.4%.

```
Real ETH Value of 1ETH (for 2/24/2022) is: 2562.792
obtained value of ETH= 2523.2095675
```

*predicted value of Ethereum

```
accuracy: 98.46%
```

*accuracy of model

*graph representing test and training datas

VII. CONCLUSION

Cryptocurrency appears to have accelerated into the early adoption stage that all new technologies go through. Bitcoin has begun to carve out a niche in the market, which might either help cryptocurrencies march toward mainstream adoption, or it could be the primary reason of their failure. Cryptocurrencies are still in their infancy, and it's difficult to say whether they'll ever become truly widespread in global markets. Because of the instability of daily exchange rates, exchange rates might move up or down. Crypto is still in its early phases as a result of this inconsistency. As a result, this implementation aids in the prediction of the crypto's rate of change utilising various data sets from various dates.

VIII. REFERENCES

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